

QUANTIFICATION OF METHANE (MARSH) GAS USING RESILIENT BACKPROPAGATION NEURAL NETWORK

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Abstract

This study unequivocally demonstrates that robust propagation neural networks can be used to quantify marsh or methane gases. Methane has lower explosive limit (LEL) is 5.0% (5000 ppm) and its upper explosive limit is 15.0% (150000 ppm) by volume with air. The main purpose of this study is to classify the concentration level below the LEL of the methane gas present in the air by using the resilient back-propagation neural network to prevent the various hazardous caused by the methane. After the suggested network was trained with defaults free parameters, it provided a very high quantification rate with two hidden layers, and tan-sigmoid activation functions. The neural network with twelve neurons in the first hidden layer and fifteen hidden neurons in the second hidden layers gives first converging rate with more accuracy. From the regression graph shows the training, validation, testing, and overall data set display high regression values that are very close to 1. The regression values quantify how closely the network outputs resemble the targets. The training, validation, testing, and overall regression values are 0.97, 1%, 0.97, and 0.98 correspondingly. This indicates that the suggested network is 98% accurate overall.

Keywords: activation function, learning algorithm, mean-square-error, methane, regression.

Introduction

The marsh gas, swamp gas or bog gas means the gases generated from the decomposition of dead component in the wetland area. The primarily compounds present in marsh gas is Methane (CH₄) along with trace quality of Carbon dioxide (CO₂), Hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) and Phosphine (PH₃). So, CH₄ is generally called as marsh gas. There are three major ways that the confined CH₄ can escape through the diffusing across an air-water interface, by the water ebullition mechanism, or by plant-mediated transport [1]. This CH₄ is a combustible gas and have lower explosive level (LEL) and upper

explosive level (UEL). The LEL of CH₄ is 5% (50000 ppm) and UEL is 15% (150000 ppm)[2]. It is very important to detect the CH₄ gas before it gets fire. The critical condition of the CH₄ is 1% (10000 ppm).

The quantification of CH₄ gas with different concentration can be done by neural network with array of sensor. The neural network can solve the highly nonlinear equations by changing its free parameter like weight, bias and activation function of the neurons [3-5]. Table 1 shows the various neural network algorithms used for classifications.

Table 1: Different neural network algorithms with their characteristic [10].

Sl. No.	Algorithms	Characteristics of the Algorithms
1	Traingd	It responds slowly and works well for training in gradual mode..
2	Traingdm	It can be used for incremental mode training and is faster than traingd.
3	Traingdx	Although it is slower than traingd, batch mode training is an option.
4	Trainrp	It converges quickly and requires little storage. Batch mode training is used in trainrp.
5	Traincgf	Out of the conjugate gradient algorithm, it requires the least amount of storage.
6	Traincgp	Although it requires a little more storage than traincgf, it converges more quickly.
7	Traincgp	Although it requires more storage than traincgp, it converges more quickly.
8	Trainscg	The only conjugate algorithm that calls for an online search is this one.
9	Trainbfg	In comparison to the conjugate gradient approach, it requires the storing of a Hessian matrix and performs more computations per iteration.
10	Trainoss	This approach strikes a balance between quasi-Newtonian methods and the conjugate gradient method.
11	Trainlm	The quickest network of moderate size training algorithm. When the training set is huge, it offers a memory reduction feature that can be used.

Among these eleven algorithms, training with resilient propagation [1] (Trainrp) has faster convergence and minimal storage. So it is the right choice for this study.

There are three main activation functions [3][6-7]. They are

Linear Transfer Function: The output of this function is linearly related to the inputs. If the input is x and the result is y . It can be represents as in fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Purelin.

2) Log-sigmoid transfer function: The output of this function ranges from 0 to 1. The relationship between the input and the output

is nonlinear. Typically, the hidden layer of a multi-layer perceptron neural network employs this transfer function. It can be represented as in fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Logsig.

3) Tan-sigmoid transfer function: The output of this function ranges from -1 to +1. The relationship between the output and the input is exponential. It can be represented as in fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Tansig.

The neural network can be train by using combination of activation function. It is desirable to take tan-sigmoid activation function as it show more promising performance reported by many researcher [8-9].

1. Scope of the Work

With the increase in concentration of methane gas in a particular area may cause explosion and health hazards. Methane gas is highly explosive in certain proportion with air (oxygen). It has lower explosive limit (LEL) is 5.0% (5000 ppm) and its upper explosive limit is 15.0% (150000 ppm) by volume with air. At higher concentration Methane gas causes simple asphyxiation because it can displace oxygen which we need for breathing. For our breathing we need minimum 18% (18000 ppm) of oxygen and if the oxygen concentration goes below 16% (16000 ppm) then is dangerous and below 10 % (10000 ppm) by volume with air is deadly. Thus detection of flammable gases like CH₄ is very important for environmental monitoring, safety of workers, and to avoid ricks of accidents range of concentration. The work flow of this study is shown in fig 04

Fig. 4: The work flow of this study.

Quantification of CH₄ using neural network.

At the very beginning, the data set are arranged divided into three groups viz. training data, validation data and testing data. The training data set is a matrix of 4x240, validation data set is 4x20 and testing data is 4x20. The total size of data set is 4x280. These data sets are the concentration of methane at 0.1%, 0.3%, 0.5% and 1% in the air.

After this the suitable neural network of two hidden layer and an output layer with twelve neurons in first hidden neuron, fifteen neurons in second hidden layers and four output neurons. The output representation or the target to the network is shown in table 2.

Table 2: Target of the neural network for different concentration.

Sl. No.	Concentration Level	Designated Output
1	0.1% of Methane	[1 0 0 0]
2	0.3% of Methane	[0 1 0 0]
3	0.5% of Methane	[0 0 1 0]
4	1% of Methane	[0 0 0 1]

There are resilient propagation (Trainrp) is a supervised learning algorithm and it is a first order optimization learning algorithm. It has faster convergence and minimal storage. So it is the most suitable training algorithm for this study. In this study a three layer neural

network is consider with all the activation as tan-sigmoid function. The designed neural network for the quantification of the methane with different concentration levels is shown fig.5.

Fig. 5: Neural Network designed for quantification of Methane.

The network is trained with default initial weights and bias, 100000 maximum numbers of epochs, with minimums gradients of 10⁻⁵. After training the network, the output graph of the network is shown in fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Neural Network output showing the convergence of training, validation and testing.

The training of the neural network is stop running at the epoch 4400 epochs after achieving the best validation performance at 1.4559⁻⁷. The mean square error (MSE) is the performance index. The lower the MSE means higher the accuracy of the network. The MSE of training and testing are quite close and approximately 10⁻² which is very good. The MSE for the validation is even lower means is very good and have less error.

data sets.

Conclusion

This study clearly shows that quantification of marsh or methane gases can be achieved by using resilient propagation neural network. After completing the of the proposed network with twelve neurons in first hidden layer, fifteen neurons hidden layer and four neuron is output layers with tan-sigmoid activation function produced very high quantification rate. Fig. 6, the regression plots of the training, validation, testing and for the whole data set shows high regression values almost near to 1. The regression values give measures of closeness between the network outputs to that of the targets. The regressions values training, validation, testing and for the whole data set are ~0.97%, ~1%, ~0.97% and ~0.98% respectively. This means the overall accuracy of the proposed network is 98%.

The regression graph of the neural network output after training is shown in fig. 6. From this figure it is observed that the regression value of the validation is 1, which means network output is showing exact to the validation data set. As for the testing and training, the regressions values are 0.96927 and 0.97268 respectively, which means the network output are value closed to the training and testing data set. The overall regression value is 0.97541, which is very closed to 1. This shows that the network outputs are quite closed to the input

Fig. 6: Neural Network output regression for training, validation and testing data sets.

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